

Catalase (CAT) Assay Kit

(Visible Light Method)

Serial No: A007-1

Pack: 100T/96S

Nanjing Jiancheng Bioengineering Institute

CATALOGUE

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1. INTRODUCTION

This kit can be used for laboratory research only.

Assay principle:

Ammonium molybdate can pause H_2O_2 decomposing reaction catalyzed by catalase (CAT) immediately, residual H_2O_2 can react with ammonium molybdate to produce a yellowish complex. It is able calculate CAT activity by measuring OD value at 405nm.

2. REAGENT COMPOSITION & PREPARATION

Reagent 1: Solution 100ml×1 bottle, can be stored at 4°C for 6 months.

Reagent 2: Substrate solution 10ml×1 bottle, can be stored at 4°C for 6 months.

Reagent 3: Chromogenic agent powder×1 bottle, can be stored at 4°C for 6 months. Add distilled water until volume reaches to 100ml, dissolve sufficiently. This preparation should be down 1 hour before assay. If there is undissolved powder at bottom, then please take supernant to use directly, this situation will not disturb results.

Reagent 4: Solution 10ml×1 bottle, can be stored at 4°C for 6 months.

It will freeze in cold days, then please put it in hot waterbath until limpid before use.

3. REQUIRED EQUIPMENTS & REAGENTS

- An spectrophotometer capable of measuring absorbance at 405nm, glass cuvettes of 0.5cm light path
- Thermostatic water bath or air bath capable of controlling temperature at 37°C

- Desk centrifuge
- Transferpettor and tips
- Vortex mixer
- A source of pure water (preferably double distilled water and double distilled water)

4. OPERATION PROCEDURES

(1) Blood serum (or plasma) CAT assay:

① Operation table:

	Contrast tube	Sample tube
Blood serum (or plasma) (ml)		0.1
Reagent 1 (37°C prewarmed) (ml)	1.0	1.0
Reagent 2 (37°C prewarmed) (ml)	0.1	0.1
Mix sufficiently, reacts at 37°C for 1 minute accurately		
Reagent 3 (ml)	1.0	1.0
Reagent 4 (ml)	0.1	0.1
Blood serum (or plasma) (ml)	0.1	
Mix sufficiently, transfer in cuvettes of 0.5cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 405nm (adjust zero by distilled water)		

② Blood serum (or plasma) CAT activity calculation:

a. Definition: 1 μ mol H₂O₂ decomposing per ml blood serum (or plasma) per second is considered as 1 activity unit (U).

b. Formula:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Blood serum (or plasma) CAT activity (U/ml)} &= (\text{OD}_{\text{Contrast}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Sample}}) \times 271^* \times \frac{1}{60 \times \text{Sampling volume}} \\ &\quad \times \text{Sampling dilution times before assay} \end{aligned}$$

Note: * 271 is reciprocal value of slope.

c. Example:

Take 0.1ml blood serum to measure CAT activity, in results, OD_{Contrast} is 0.720, OD_{Sample} is 0.675. Calculate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Blood serum (or plasma) CAT activity (U/ml)} &= (0.720 - 0.675) \times 271 \times \frac{1}{60 \times 0.1} \times 1 = 2.03 \text{ U/ml} \end{aligned}$$

In order to operate expediently, you can do all preparations at first, label all test tubes by number, add 0.1ml sample and 1ml Reagent 1, then put all test tubes in 37°C water bath for 3~5 minutes. During operation, add 0.1ml Reagent 2, count time accurately at the same time, mix sufficiently immediately, place in 37°C water bath, when t=1min, add chromogenic agent immediately and terminate reaction, mix sufficiently. Then you can operate Tube 2, Tube 3...contrast tube & sample tube. Contrast tube and sample tube must be measured at same time.

(2) 1:99 hemolysate CAT assay:

① **1:99 hemolysate preparation:** Take 50 μ l whole blood, add distilled water until volume reaches to 5ml, place for 10 minutes and then you can start assay.

② Operation table:

	Blank contrast tube	Sample tube	Self contrast tube
Distilled water (ml)	0.05		2.1
1:99 hemolysate (ml)		0.05	0.05
Reagent 1 (37°C prewarmed) (ml)	1.0	1.0	
Reagent 2 (37°C prewarmed) (ml)	0.1	0.1	
Mix sufficiently, reacts at 37°C for 1 minute accurately			
Reagent 3 (ml)	1.0	1.0	
Mix sufficiently, transfer in cuvettes of 0.5cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 405nm (adjust zero by distilled water)			

③ Hemoglobin CAT activity calculation:

a. Definition: 1 μ mol H₂O₂ decomposing per mg hemoglobin per second is considered as 1 activity unit (U).

b. Formula:

$$\text{CAT activity (U/mgHb)} = \frac{(\text{OD}_{\text{Blank contrast}} + \text{OD}_{\text{Self contrast}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Sample}}) \times \frac{271^* \times 1}{60 \times \text{Sampling volume}}}{\text{Hemoglobin (mgHb/ml)}}$$

Note: * 271 is reciprocal value of slope.

c. Example:

Take 0.05ml 1:99 mouse hemolysate to measure CAT activity, in results, OD_{Blank contrast} is 0.569, OD_{Self contrast} is 0.105, OD_{Sample} is 0.516, hemoglobin content in 1:99 hemolysate is 1.324mgHb/ml Calculate as follows:

$$\text{Hemolysate CAT activity (U/mgHb)} = (0.569 + 0.105 - 0.516) \times 271 \times \frac{1}{60 \times 0.05} \div 1.324 = 10.78 \text{ U/mgHb}$$

(3) Tissue homogenate CAT assay:

① **Tissue homogenate preparation:** Weigh tissue accurately, add 9 times distilled water to make 10% tissue homogenate, centrifugate at 2500rpm for 10 minutes. Take supernatant, dilute with physiological saline to optimal sampling concentration for assay (you can read optimal sampling concentration probing in appendix).

② Operation table:

	Contrast tube	Sample tube
Tissue homogenate (ml)		0.05
Reagent 1 (37°C prewarmed) (ml)	1.0	1.0
Reagent 2 (37°C prewarmed) (ml)	0.1	0.1
Mix sufficiently, reacts at 37°C for 1 minute accurately		
Reagent 3 (ml)	1.0	1.0
Reagent 4 (ml)	0.1	0.1
Tissue homogenate (ml)	0.05	
Mix sufficiently, transfer in cuvettes of 0.5cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 405nm (adjust zero by distilled water)		

③ Tissue homogenate CAT activity calculation:

a. Definition: $1\mu\text{mol H}_2\text{O}_2$ decomposing per mg tissue protein per second is considered as 1 activity unit (U).

b. Formula:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tissue homogenate} \\ \text{CAT activity} \\ (\text{U/mgprot}) \end{aligned} &= (\text{OD}_{\text{Contrast}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Sample}}) \times 271^* \\ &\times \frac{1}{60 \times \text{Sampling volume}} \div \text{Protein concentration} \\ &\quad \text{in tissue homogenate} \\ &\quad \text{(mgprot/ml)} \end{aligned}$$

Note: * 271 is reciprocal value of slope.

c. Examples:

① Take 0.05ml 0.5% rat liver tissue homogenate to measure CAT activity, in results, $\text{OD}_{\text{Contrast}}$ is 0.671, $\text{OD}_{\text{Sample}}$ is 0.445, protein content in 0.5% rat liver tissue homogenate is 0.48mgprot/ml Calculate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tissue homogenate} \\ \text{CAT activity} \\ (\text{U/mgprot}) \end{aligned} &= (0.671 - 0.445) \times 271 \times \frac{1}{60 \times 0.05} \div 0.48 = 42.53 \text{ U/mgprot}$$

② Take 0.05ml 5% earthworm tissue homogenate to measure CAT activity, in results, $\text{OD}_{\text{Contrast}}$ is 0.605, $\text{OD}_{\text{Sample}}$ is 0.425, protein content in 5% earthworm tissue homogenate is 3.1158mgprot/ml Calculate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tissue homogenate} \\ \text{CAT activity} \\ (\text{U/mgprot}) \end{aligned} &= (0.605 - 0.425) \times 271 \times \frac{1}{60 \times 0.05} \div 3.1158 = 5.2185 \text{ U/mgprot}$$

③ Take 0.05ml 10% rice leaf homogenate to measure CAT activity, in results, $\text{OD}_{\text{Contrast}}$ is 0.704, $\text{OD}_{\text{Sample}}$ is 0.332, protein content in 10% rice leaf homogenate is 3.1303mgprot/ml Calculate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tissue homogenate} \\ \text{CAT activity} \\ (\text{U/mgprot}) \end{aligned} &= (0.704 - 0.332) \times 271 \times \frac{1}{60 \times 0.05} \div 3.1303 = 10.7351 \text{ U/mgprot}$$

④ Take 0.05ml 0.5% *Acipenser sinensis* liver tissue homogenate to measure CAT activity, in results, $\text{OD}_{\text{Contrast}}$ is 0.580, $\text{OD}_{\text{Sample}}$ is 0.426, protein content in 0.5% *Acipenser sinensis* liver tissue homogenate is 0.3063mgprot/ml Calculate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tissue homogenate} \\ \text{CAT activity} \\ (\text{U/mgprot}) \end{aligned} &= (0.580 - 0.503) \times 271 \times \frac{1}{60 \times 0.05} \div 0.3063 = 22.7058 \text{ U/mgprot}$$

5. ANNOUNCEMENTS

(1) When you do blood serum (or plasma) CAT assay, if there is no hemolysis in samples, then you just need to take 2 random samples for contrast per batch or use double distilled water for contrast; if there is hemolysis, then you must make contrast tube for each sample.

(2) When do tissue homogenate CAT assay, if there is no hyperlipemia, then you just need to take 2 random samples for contrast per batch or use double distilled water for contrast; if there is hyperlipemia, then you must make contrast tube for each sample.

(3) When you do whole blood CAT assay, you must make contrast tube for each sample.

6. ABOUT COMPANY

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APPENDIX: OPTIMAL SAMPLING VOLUME PROBING

- 1. Reagents & preparation:** Offered and prepared according to manual by Nanjing Jiancheng Bioengineering Institue 1st substation,
- 2. Sample source:** Normal mouse liver tissue, make 10% homogenate, then dilute with physiological saline to different concentrations.
- 3. Operation Unit:** Jiancheng detection department
- 4. Operation table:**

	Contrast tube	Sample tube
Tissue homogenate (ml)		0.05
Reagent 1 (37°C prewarmed) (ml)	1.0	1.0
Reagent 2 (37°C prewarmed) (ml)	0.1	0.1
Mix sufficiently, reacts at 37°C for 1 minute accurately		
Reagent 3 (ml)	1.0	1.0
Reagent 4 (ml)	0.1	0.1
Tissue homogenate (ml)	0.05	
Mix sufficiently, transfer in cuvettes of 0.5cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 405nm (adjust zero by distilled water)		

5. Results

Homogenate concentration (%)	OD ₁	OD ₂	Average OD	△OD
0.125	0.613	0.612	0.613	0.058
0.25	0.556	0.560	0.558	0.113
0.5	0.440	0.449	0.445	0.226
1	0.258	0.258	0.258	0.413
2	0.058	0.059	0.059	0.612
5	0.021	0.018	0.020	0.651
10	0.032	0.031	0.032	0.639
Contrast tube	0.669	0.673	0.671	

6. Mouse liver tissue optimal sampling concentration probing curve:

Referenced sampling concentration: 0.25%~1%. In this range, enzyme curve appears direct proportion relatively after regression curve treatment. If sampling concentration is too high or too low, then results won't appear significant deviation after statistical treatment.

